

Techno-Economic Assessment of Biochar Adsorption for the Treatment of Surface Water

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Abstract

This study aims to propose a cost-effective solution for addressing the global challenge of water scarcity by exploring the use of biochar in a downflow fixed bed adsorption system for the removal of contaminants from surface water. The process parameters were optimized using a commonly used antibiotic, sulfamethoxazole. The Clark model provided the best fit to the data, suggesting its potential for accurately predicting the breakthrough curve. The system's reusability was also assessed through an advanced continuous regeneration method. Its applicability was further validated by real-case surface water treatment tests, accompanied by comprehensive pollutant analysis. A techno-economic assessment revealed a unit cost of less than 1 euro/m³, demonstrating the system's commercial viability. This study underscores the potential of biochar as a cost-effective water treatment solution for large-scale applications.

Keywords: Antibiotics removal; Biochar adsorption; Continuous flow; Filtration; Economic viability analysis.

INTRODUCTION

High turbidity and the presence of pollutants in water sources represent serious threats to both environmental safety and public health, highlighting the need for effective treatment solutions to ensure clean and safe water (Xu et al., 2023). Emerging contaminants are progressively polluting water resources, contributing to the rise in antibiotic resistance (Huang et al., 2022). Cleaning water is crucial for environmental safety and public health (Pratap et al., 2023). For this reason, there is an urgent need to improve treatment processes that can effectively remove traces of contaminants and be applied either before or after conventional water treatment. Among various treatment methods, such as advanced oxidation processes, osmotic processes, and membrane filtration, adsorption stands out as a promising approach due to its cost-effectiveness in treating organic pollutants (Bizi, 2020). Biochar, a low-cost adsorbent material, can effectively treat micro-pollutants (Baaloudj et al., 2025). Batch adsorption is indeed the most common application, but continuous adsorption column systems are more feasible for industrial applications (Huang et al., 2022). To evaluate a process, rapid small-scale column tests provide a quicker and more efficient alternative, generating breakthroughs within hours or days (Zietzschmann et al., 2014). This study investigates the feasibility of using biochar in a downflow fixed bed adsorption system for removing contaminants from water as a sustainable and cost-effective solution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Analytical-grade chemicals were used in this study, including sulfamethoxazole, sodium persulfate, ultrapure water, HPLC/MS quality water, acetonitrile, and methanol. Surface water was collected from a river in the south of Italy. The biochar was provided by Terra Fertilis (France) and was produced through the pyrolysis of wood pellets. The SMX solution with 5 mg/L (for optimization) and surface water was passed through the biochar column featuring a biochar mass of 23 g, a bed height of 12.5 cm, and column dimensions (internal diameter of 2.5 cm and length of 17 cm) with a flow rate of around 10 mL/min for testing the treatment performance. The efficiency of the process was evaluated by following the concentration of pollutants before and after treatment. The SMX concentrations were followed using HPLC Agilent Technologies®. An analytical protocol based on solid-phase extraction (HLB Oasis, 6 cc, 500 mg), pre-concentration, and further measurement by UHPLC-MS/MS was used for water screening in the analysis of surface water. Turbidity was also followed by a Turbidimeter. Adsorption modeling was performed using four models established by Thomas, Adams–Bohart, Yoon–Nelson and Clark to evaluate the column behavior, efficiency, and applicability in large-scale operations (Matolia et al., 2019). To regenerate the column, a continuous mode regeneration method using thermally activated persulfate (PS) was

employed (Baaloudj et al., 2025). The reusability was assessed over many adsorption-regeneration cycles. The temperature for thermal PS activation was adjusted to 60 °C and the concentration was in optimal value [PS]= 20 mM (Deng et al., 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adsorption of SMX for Modeling and Regeneration

The study investigates the efficacy of an adsorption process in continuous surface treatment, specifically for SMX removal using biochar columns. A test for SMX removal was performed with the parameters 10 mL/min for flow rate and 5.5 cm (10 g) for bed depth (biochar weight), with an initial concentration of 5 mg/L and pH natural. The results are shown in Figure 1 (a), showing effective removal with a saturation time of around 20 hours, which is effective. Adams-Bohart, Thomas, Yoon-Nelson, and Clark breakthrough curve models were used to analyze the adsorption process (Djelloul and Hamdaoui, 2015). As shown in Figure 1 (b), the Clark model was well-fitted to the data, indicating their potential use in describing the adsorption process in this column. The surface analysis by XPS showed the expected variability among the sampled layers for biochar as it is and the one after adsorption. Figure 1 (c) presents the XPS analysis of biochar before and after the adsorption. The interaction of contaminants with the biochar surface is evident from the changes in the XPS spectra such as the appearance of N1s, S2s, and S2p, indicating the effective adsorption of SMX which means removal from the water. To address the saturation of biochar, a regeneration method was assessed for SMX removal. The regeneration solution consisted of heat-activated persulfate at a concentration of 20 mM (Deng et al., 2023), which decomposes the adsorbed SMX into smaller, less harmful compounds. The regeneration process was repeated for five cycles, with the second cycle demonstrating 82% greater effectiveness than the first, that is maybe because the impurities in the sample after pyrolysis have been removed after regeneration. The system maintained a significant adsorption capacity after multiple cycles, retaining 60% efficiency even after 20 hours of operation in each cycle.

Figure 1. (a) Breakthrough curve for SMX removal 5mg/L with flow rate 10 ml/min and bed depth 5.5 cm, (b) Clark modeling for breakthrough curve, (c) XPS analysis for samples before and after adsorption, (d) regeneration for 5 cycles.

Treatment of Surface water

The performance of the process in treating surface water needs to be evaluated with realistic water samples. Under optimal conditions, a biochar fixed-bed column was utilized in a continuous treatment of surface water. Non-target analysis was evaluated, and turbidity was monitored during treatment. Results showed a significant reduction in turbidity from 22 NTU before treatment to 4.8 NTU after treatment. This reduction is suitable for processed food crops and unrestricted irrigation for vegetables, and wastewater discharge limits typically target <5 NTU for environmental safety (Jeong et al., 2016). Moreover, the proposed system demonstrated significant improvements in water quality, effectively reducing the presence of multicomponent mixtures in surface water, where the detected compounds and their removal efficiencies were 61.44% for salicylic acid, 74.12% for furosemide, 52.34% for losartan, 85.4% for sulfamethoxazole, 100% for carbamazepine. Table 1 highlights the pollutants detected and subsequently removed by the biochar system.

Table 1. Pollutants that were detected and removed from surface water.

Contaminants	Removal efficiency
Salicylic acid	61.44%
Furosemide	74.12%
Losartan	52.34%
Sulfamethoxazole	85.4 %
Carbamazepine	100%

Figure 2. Turbidity level of surface water before and after treatment.

Techno-Economic Evaluation

The engineering design and cost estimation investigations for a biochar adsorption system were conducted. The design was based on prior experimental results and conditions. The following scaling factor was used to estimate parameters from small to larger scales, where it was calculated based on a target flow rate (10 L/min), the calculated parameters are shown in Table 2.

$$\text{Scaling Factor} = \frac{Q_{\text{scaled up}}}{Q_{\text{original}}} \quad (1)$$

Based on the new calculated parameters and dimensions, a treatment system has been proposed (Figure 3) consisting of two parallel columns, each 170 cm in length and 25.9 cm in internal diameter, operating alternately to ensure continuous operation without interruption. While one column adsorbs pollutants and treats water, the other undergoes regeneration using an activated persulfate solution, followed by water rinse. This dual-function system enhances treatment performance and time efficiency, offering a more sustainable approach by separating pollutants from treated water and regenerating them separately. This method helps prevent by-product formation and avoids potential pollution issues commonly associated with conventional treatments.

The economic feasibility evaluation was evaluated based on previously established conditions. The total cost of fabricating and implementing the proposed system was estimated to be €1500, with each column costing approximately €204. The treatment cost was calculated at €0.8 per cubic meter, which is deemed acceptable for a treatment system.

Table 2. Economic evaluation for the proposed water treatment system.

Parameter	Value
Flow rate	10 L/min
No. of working days per year	288 days/year
Treated wastewater	14.4 m ³ /day
Treatment time by cycle	130 hours
Column volume	83.5 L
Internal diameter	25.9 cm
Length	170 cm
Column system (stainless steel)	€204.0
Total fabrication cost	€1500
Biochar cost	€0.34/m ³
Estimated operating costs	€0.25/m ³
Regeneration solution	€0.03/m ³
Energy consumption cost	€0.18/m ³
Estimated treatment cost	€0.8/m ³

Figure 3. The engineering design of the treatment system.**Acknowledgement:**

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